

SIMULATIONS TO CHARACTERIZE A PASSIVE MICROWAVE BLACKBODY DESIGN*

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the design of a microwave blackbody to be used as a primary laboratory standard for passive remote sensing applications. This temperature adjustable design is required to operate and be fully characterized from 10 to 220 GHz. We discuss the challenges involved in designing this type of calibration source and address how improvements can be made to increase performance over blackbodies typically flown on airborne and space-borne instruments. A simplified electromagnetic model for absorber layer optimization is introduced as the precursor to a finite-element, full-wave solution for the calculation of emissivity. A temperature simulation predicts the physical temperature of the blackbody and surrounding chamber. The simulated data are used as inputs to a rigorous calculation of the microwave brightness temperature radiated by the blackbody source. This calculation provides an estimate of the offset between measured physical temperature and radiometrically measured brightness temperature.

Index Terms—remote sensing; blackbody; passive microwave; calibration; design; simulation

1. INTRODUCTION

Measurements from passive microwave radiometers are critical to the accuracy of numerical weather models used worldwide for weather forecasting and climate modeling [1]. There is currently no national or International System of Units (SI) traceability standard for microwave brightness temperature (T_B). The result of this is that no microwave data has a quantifiable accuracy referenced to a ‘true’ value, and the long term records contain instrument-to-instrument offsets as each new instrument uses a differently performing T_B reference source.

At the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) we are working to develop such a standard and already possess much of the hardware and have developed the measurement methodology to realize a standard free-space T_B calibration [2]. By utilizing the NIST standard radiometer as the primary reference we are able to achieve a nominal minimum calibration uncertainty of about ± 0.7 K in the frequency range of 18 GHz to 26.5 GHz [3]. If instead a well characterized ‘blackbody’ source was used as a primary reference, this uncertainty could be reduced below ± 0.3 K [4]. The term blackbody is placed in quotations as this is purely a theoretical concept and can only be physically approximated.

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For the remainder of the paper, the term will be used without quotations to refer to a passive microwave calibration source.

The primary requirements driving the design process are emissivity and temperature distribution. In order to closely approximate the theoretical blackbody, the source should have a microwave emissivity close to unity, and to be describable by a single temperature it should have a uniform physical temperature distribution. These are the focus of the simulations discussed herein.

Typical airborne and space-borne instruments are constrained by both mass and volume, so naturally the design of the blackbody used in these instruments reflects these constraints. A benefit of designing a standard intended only for laboratory use is that these mass and volume constraints are significantly relaxed. The volume-saving flight geometry nominally consists of an aluminum array of square pyramids coated with a thin layer of iron-doped epoxy absorber. This design can provide excellent performance over narrow frequency ranges, but the frequencies of peak performance are highly dependent on the pyramid dimensions [5]. For this type of design, a heater is placed on the flat backside of the pyramid array, the tips of the pyramids are further from the heater, resulting in temperature gradients along the pyramidal axes. These temperature gradients have been studied [6, 7] and are recognized as a reason to investigate alternative blackbody configurations [8].

In cases where mass and volume are not as constrained, there has recently been some use of state-of-the-art geometries. Investigation has shown that a large hollow cone structure can offer higher emissivity than the traditional pyramidal arrays [8, 9]. To cover the vast majority of climate sensitive remote sensing bands, the NIST standard aims to cover the frequency range between 10 and 220 GHz. It will be shown that these large non-periodic designs are well suited to cover this large frequency spectrum. The following sections describe the process of simulating and optimizing these modern geometries for use as the NIST primary broadband blackbody standard.

2. ELECTROMAGNETIC SIMULATIONS

By reciprocity, if a passive body is an efficient absorber it is also an efficient emitter. Accordingly, we wish to maximize absorbance, which in the lack of transmission, by conservation of energy, also means minimizing reflections. Two approaches were used in the electromagnetic simulations of the blackbody designs. The first method uses a geometric-optics high-frequency approximation to simplify the optimization of the microwave absorber coating. The second method uses commercial finite element modeling (FEM) software to

rigorously solve the 3-dimensional Maxwell equations on the full-scale, optimized design geometry.

2.1. Absorber layer optimization

Iron-doped epoxy absorber is lossy at microwave frequencies and is widely used in microwave blackbody construction. We examine different variations of Eccosorb¹ CR absorber material; CR110, CR114, and CR117. Differing fill fractions, or concentrations, of iron particles suspended in the epoxy provides varying electrical properties. The complex permittivity and permeability for the materials investigated are provided up to 140 GHz in [10]. At frequencies above that, the parameters remain relatively constant and are extrapolated up to 220 GHz. Material characterization for these materials and other absorber types is underway at NIST to confirm the results in [10], but the data were not yet available for this study.

A simplistic geometric optics (GO) model was created to aid in optimization of the microwave absorber layering on the cone. By layering different types of absorber, we aim to minimize surface reflections at the air-absorber interface while maximizing absorption loss of the microwaves propagating within the absorber. The GO model assumes a uniform incident plane wave and perfect specular reflection. The analysis here is also limited to 2 dimensions. The model calculates the oblique incidence reflection coefficients and then calculates the total reflection from the multilayer assembly including multipath between each interface. The formulation was followed from [11] and [12]. The objective function to be minimized is given by,

$$F(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{a}, f) = R(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{a}, f) + |\sum_1^n T_n - T_{des}| \quad (1)$$

where F is the scalar objective function value to be minimized, R is the total calculated reflection magnitude from multilayer assembly, T_{des} is the desired total thickness, n is the number of layers, \mathbf{T} is a length n vector of individual layer thicknesses T_n , \mathbf{a} is a length n vector indicating the corresponding absorber type for each layer, f is the frequency of evaluation. The second term on the right hand side of (1) ensures that the resulting optimal thickness values in fact sum to the desired total absorber thickness by penalizing the objective function.

We choose to limit the investigation to 3 absorber layers for practical manufacturability concerns. An outer insulation layer is included in the analysis, and the total absorber thickness is limited to 1 mm, the necessity for these constraints is due to thermal effects and is discussed in the following section. The absorber material will be cast onto an aluminum or copper substrate structure so the bottom boundary in the analysis was considered a perfectly conducting boundary layer. It was determined from initial single-material single-layer run of the full wave solution that the models were experiencing the highest reflections around 23 GHz so the optimization was first run at this frequency. We then also ran the optimization at 60 GHz. Though we allowed three layers, two of the adjacent layers in the resulting solution were the same material so the optimal setup found for both of the frequencies was two layers.

¹Eccosorb is a registered trademark of Emerson & Cuming Microwave Products. NIST does not endorse this product or company; other products may be suitable for this application

For a 10 degree cone or wedge angle at 23 GHz, the optimal configuration consists of a 0.40 mm layer of CR114 on top of a 0.60 mm layer of CR110. For the 60 GHz case, the optimal configuration is a 0.63 mm layer of CR117 on top of a 0.37 mm layer of CR110. These optimal values are used as geometry and material inputs to the full wave FEM solver.

2.2. Finite Element full wave solution

To obtain an accurate prediction of the performance of the blackbody designs, the commercial FEM package HFSS² is used to solve the full 3-dimensional Maxwell equations and calculate the emissivity of the design.

The 3-dimensional dual-layer absorber configuration with a 3 mm insulation layer is modeled in the software and the material parameters are input along with their frequency dependencies. The model is then excited with uniform plane waves at various incidence angles independently and the scattered far-field electric field pattern is calculated. Polarization of the reflected field is not considered because the emitted blackbody radiation will be non-polarized, and we are only considering calibration of total-power radiometers. The solutions at each incidence angle are integrated to obtain the emissivity according to [13],

$$\varepsilon(\theta) = 1 - \int_{\Omega} \frac{|E_r(\theta, \Omega)|^2 r^2}{|E_i(\theta)|^2 A \cos(\theta)} d\Omega \quad (2)$$

where ε is emissivity, E_r is the reflected electric field, E_i is the incident electric field, A is the cross sectional area of the blackbody aperture, r is the corresponding radius of the reflected field, Ω is the solid-angle of scattering hemisphere, and θ is the incidence angle. We have assumed that the blackbody is rotationally symmetric, removing any dependency of the incident wave on ϕ . Figure 1 shows the normal incidence emissivity versus frequency. This value is convenient for making relative comparisons of design performance, the rigorous integration of the emissivity for target T_B calculation will be introduced in a subsequent section.

Because of the computational and post-processing expensive nature of the emissivity analysis, the emissivity is calculated only at discrete frequencies of interest for remote sensing applications. The simulation was first run using the 23

Figure 1. Normal incidence emissivity versus frequency

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GHz optimized absorber layering and an emissivity dip at 60 GHz was noticed. The absorber was then optimized at 60 GHz which provided some improvement at 60 GHz but showed much worse performance at 118 GHz. The difference between the 8° and 10° cone angle was shown to be negligible. A 12° cone was also simulated but had poorer performance and is not shown here. The 10° cone angle is desirable because it allows optimal performance and a more compact blackbody than the 8° at a given aperture diameter.

3. TEMPERATURE SIMULATIONS

The physical temperature on the radiating surface of the blackbody is the other critical variable for quantifying its T_B . Free-space laboratory radiometer calibrations at NIST are performed in an anechoic chamber. Pre-launch calibration of satellite-borne instruments may also be performed in a thermal-vacuum (TVC) chamber. We will simulate the physical temperature of the radiating surface of the blackbodies in the anechoic chamber and in the TVC. The anechoic chamber is equipped with circulation fans to maintain a steady background temperature when there are active heat sources. The air circulation in the chamber creates a forced convection scenario on the blackbody from a heat transfer perspective. For the anechoic chamber case we simulate the convective and radiative heat loss, but in the TVC radiation is the only heat loss mechanism.

The anechoic chamber along with the circulation fans is drawn in CAD software and the conical blackbody target is placed within the chamber. A commercial FEM computational fluid dynamics software called ANSYS CFX³ is used to perform the thermal simulations. The carbon-loaded foam absorber lining the anechoic chamber is highly insulating so the walls are assigned as an adiabatic boundary condition. The backside of the aluminum substrate is assigned as an isothermal surface with a temperature equal to a typical target temperature value of 350 K. The thermal infrared emissivity of the absorber material was determined from the empirical fitting method described in [14]. The fans are defined as inlet and outlet boundary conditions with the appropriate mass flow rate of air. The software package includes turbulence modeling and boundary layer effects for an accurate analysis of the convective airflow and radiation exchange in the system. We simulate the steady-state temperature distribution on the blackbody absorber surface. Steady-state is a good assumption here because in practice we allow ample time for the system to reach thermal equilibrium.

Initial results showed large temperature gradients along the absorber surface, particularly on the edges of the conical structure. We decided to investigate the use of a thin layer of closed-cell polyethylene foam to reduce heat transfer. A 3 mm layer of insulation was shown to significantly reduce the temperature gradient while having little effect on the electromagnetic behavior of the absorber. This was proven in section 2 as this 3 mm insulation layer was included in the simulations of section 2.1 and 2.2. Figure 2 shows the blackbody in the chamber with the outlined inlet and outlet

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fans. Figure 3 shows the simulated temperature distribution on the absorber surface. The vacuum case showed similar temperature gradients because thermal radiation is the dominant heat loss mechanism.

The temperature distribution data and corresponding coordinates are output to a file to be used in the full effective target T_B calculation detailed in the proceeding section.

Figure 2. Temperature simulation setup

Figure 3. Temperature distribution on non-insulated absorber surface for nominal 350 K heater setting temperature, view is looking into cone

4. BRIGHTNESS TEMPERATURE (T_B) CALCULATION

In prior NIST measurements of blackbody targets we made some assumptions about the blackbody and background temperature to simplify the analysis. We assumed that the physical temperatures of both were spatially uniform with values equal to the average of their temperature sensor's readings [3]. This assumption allows the blackbody and background T_B contributions to be expressed as single scalar values independent of the measuring antenna pattern. This is

critical to the calibration method and allows us to make measurements with any antenna without independent quantification of the antenna pattern. The radiometer measurement can be expressed according to [3],

$$T_x = \alpha(T_B^{bb} + T_B^{bg}) + (1 - \alpha)T_{phy}^{ant}, \quad (3)$$

where the blackbody brightness temperature contribution, T_B^{bb} , is given by,

$$T_B^{bb} \approx \frac{\int_{bb} T_{bb}(\theta, \varphi) \varepsilon(\theta) F_n(\theta, \varphi) d\Omega}{\int_{4\pi} F_n(\theta, \varphi) d\Omega}, \quad (4)$$

and the background brightness temperature contribution, T_B^{bg} , is given by,

$$T_B^{bg} \approx \frac{\int_{bg} T_{bg}(\theta, \varphi) \varepsilon_{bg}(\theta, \varphi) F_n(\theta, \varphi) d\Omega}{\int_{4\pi} F_n(\theta, \varphi) d\Omega} \quad (5)$$

where T_x is the measured radiometer T_B , α is the antenna radiation efficiency, T_{phy}^{ant} is the physical temperature of the antenna, T_{bb} is the physical temperature of the blackbody, ε is the emissivity of the target, F_n is the normalized antenna power pattern, T_{bg} is the physical temperature of the background, and ε_{bg} is the emissivity of the background. The numerator in (4) is integrated over the solid angle subtended by the blackbody, whereas the numerator in (5) is integrated over the remainder of the 4π steradians, what we call the background. The approximation signs in (4) and (5) refer to the Rayleigh-Jeans approximation which is a robust assumption at the frequencies and T_B s of interest [15]. The simulation results discussed in sections 2 and 3 allow a full rigorous integration of the target T_B^{bb} contribution of (4). We used simulated antenna pattern data and interpolated the temperature gradients onto the spherical coordinate grid. The full integration has been performed for the insulated blackbody design at 18 GHz and 26.5 GHz, and the the backside heater temperature and the blackbody brightness temperature, T_B^{bb} , agree within 0.048 K and 0.036 K for the two frequencies respectively. Future work will expand this analysis to more frequencies in the design spectrum to fully quantify the blackbody performance and estimated measurement uncertainty when using the method developed in [3]. We will also examine the rigorous background brightness temperature contribution term in the analysis of the total calibration uncertainty.

5. CONCLUSION

The computational and analytical simulations discussed in this paper allow optimization of a blackbody design and a rigorous calculation its measurable T_B . This method quantifies the robustness of the frequently made assumption that the T_B is equivalent to the physical temperature. Whether the assumption is valid or not depends on the blackbody emissivity and temperature performance, as well as the setup geometry and the accuracy requirements of the associated measurement application.

With the trends in high performance hardware, the accuracy required for radiometer calibration is also increasing. At NIST, with the development of a T_B standard, we intend to calibrate next generation microwave instruments and provide customers with a calibration report and associated calibration uncertainty. The blackbody design discussed here has superior performance to the traditional design geometry [14] and will enable the calibration uncertainties required for the future.

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